

Competition Versus Collaboration Business Model: A Review

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Abstract:- Competitive and collaborative business models exist in business. Organizational leaders are realizing that even their best individual efforts are insufficient to address today's complex and interwoven issues and are beginning to put their interests aside and work together to create a new business infrastructure that will help them achieve their common goals. Conversely, many organizations have also been unjustly drawn into these alliances when their fundamental need remains to sharpen their competitive drive, rather than dull it through collaboration with other firms. The reality is that both Competition and Collaboration have weaknesses, this study investigates these two business models and their relevance and recommends that hybridization of the two models can help build organizational strength in today's complex market.

Keywords:- Competition; Collaboration; Business; Model; Technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to [1], competition means to seek or strive for something in opposition to others, to vie for a prize, while collaboration, on the other hand, is defined as working together (often enviously, with an adversary). Banks offer a variety of services offline, retaining a large number of customers, and they also offer online banking services, allowing customers to meet their needs 24/7, without having to go to a teller [2]. Banks have also started to improve their services, cut expenses, and focus on more profitable areas. However, there are obstacles to overcome, such as adapting to a changing environment and convincing users to utilize online banking [3].

Moreso, banks operate primarily electronically, and they have a track record of establishing external systems such as ATMs and phone banking. Users who were already familiar with these technologies transitioned seamlessly to Internet banking. On the other hand, the juggle of fundamental banking processes with information technology could be difficult and time-consuming, especially because it is a different area entirely, and competing with core IT businesses for these services could be difficult [3]. This is where the competition versus collaboration decision has to be wisely made.

According to research findings by [4] and [2], new kinds of corporate collaboration can improve sustainability and develop better products and services, Leaders and organizations are also realizing that their greatest efforts alone will not be enough to solve today's complex and linked problems. They are putting their interests aside and working together to create a new civic infrastructure that will help them achieve their common goals [4]. As a result, all organizations, whether known or not, and whether explicit or not, have some form of composite strategy in their operations; some of these strategies, even if implicit or emergent, appear to be workable and effective; and the basic problem that all organizations must deal with, even if many do not face up to this task explicitly, is how to formulate a hybrid strategy that adds to, rather than detracts from, the company's overall sustainable advantage [4].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[5] Investigated competition through collaboration in the Turkish textile supply chain as a consequence of an endeavor to acquire a better knowledge of the benefits, bridges, and barriers associated with supply chain collaboration. The study is based on observations made during a thorough field assessment of a productive partnership in the Turkish dyeing and finishing sector. The findings show that supplier chain vs supply chain is quickly replacing company against the firm as the mode of corporate competitiveness. Thanks to the knowledge gleaned through the collaborative method used in this textile supply chain, the advantages, solutions, and obstacles connected with supply chain collaboration are also well understood.

Variables that encourage collaboration, trust, shared objectives, and the presence of mechanisms for cooperation are mentioned. However, impediments to collaboration are attributed to three things: a lack of trust, a lack of risk-benefit analysis, and a lack of shared objectives. The study's findings, regrettably, are based on questionnaires and interviews with executives from 3T, 30 dyeing and finishing businesses—10 of which are partners—and six technology-supplier partner companies from diverse regions of Turkey. However, in managing collaborations, the study emphasizes the importance of trust and cooperation mechanisms. Collaborations can help textile companies compete more effectively, as the story of 3T in the dyeing and finishing business demonstrates.

In the context of IT development, [6] investigate the role of collaboration and competitiveness among teammates. Collaboration and competition are frequently thought to be opposite poles of a shared spectrum of group behavior. This study, on the other hand, views intra-team collaboration and rivalry as two distinct and independent constructs, to determine the impact of each on project performance. In this study, quantitative methodologies were used to assess 176 IT projects from Motorola and some of its partner companies. The findings indicate that collaboration has a significant impact on project performance, but the rivalry has a minor impact. The conclusions of the study are then distilled into principles for comprehending productive project teams.

[7] Looked at the effects of competition on employees' willingness to cooperate. The study pits three groups of employees against three economic contexts with varying degrees of competition, ranging from no competition at all to perfect competition. In the absence of competition, employees give significantly to a public initiative, but they contribute very little when there is a high level of competition. As the level of competition rises, there is a distinct shift in attitude toward collaboration. According to the findings, if cooperation improves well-being, the highest level of competitiveness may not be efficient.

[8] Discusses the creation of collaborative networks between organizations in circular cities. A two-stage game is used in the model. Organizations create collaboration linkages in the first stage and then participate in pricing rivalry in the second step. A generalization of Salop's (1979) model is used in the second step. The paper investigates network pairwise stability and a stochastic network development mechanism. Furthermore, the research identifies socially efficient networks. The study, on the other hand, fails to narrow down its focus to demonstrate how implementable the model is.

[9] Investigated the relationship between competition and efficiency and discovered that it is commonly assumed that stronger competition means more active firms, which helps consumers and pushes antitrust authorities to promote competition. His research, however, demonstrates that this view might be misleading and that increased competition may harm consumers. According to the report, antitrust regulators should focus on reducing inefficiency rather than enhancing competition by adding new firms. Unfortunately, no model to address these issues was developed as part of this research.

The effect of collaborative research and development initiatives on corporate innovation was examined by [10]. According to the paper, a company can boost innovation through internal research and development (R&D) projects or by creating external collaborative R&D alliances. [10] contend that little has been done to examine the simultaneous impact of competitive and non-competitive R&D collaborations on firm innovation, despite the fact that earlier research on R&D collaboration and knowledge diffusion has mainly focused on various external sources of R&D collaboration. University-based non-competitive R&D

partnerships have a favorable direct effect on a company's innovation performance. The link between a firm's internal R&D activities and firm innovation is positively moderated by both competitive and non-competitive R&D collaborations, with the positive moderating effect being greater for non-competitive collaborations. Despite the findings of the study showing that R&D collaborations, whether non-competitive or competitive, reflect the nature of a win-win situation and have implications for enterprises' decisions about R&D alliance partners and governmental laws, no model for a solution is provided.

[11] Conducted research and published a study on workplace collaboration in Australia. It expands on earlier studies Google commissioned on the economic impact of the internet and the use of digital technology in contemporary businesses. This paper evaluates workplace collaboration in Australia and offers recommendations on how businesses may adapt to new trends in workplace collaboration. The research examines important facets of the role that collaboration plays in the contemporary economy, such as its importance to the economy, advantages for businesses and employees, as well as challenges and hurdles. Unfortunately, no collaborative business model was developed or recommended by the study.

Using an agent-based modeling method, [12] studied how competition and collaboration affect supply chain performance. According to [12], ideal supply chain collaboration is difficult to attain in practice, and one issue that is thought to hamper collaboration is company competitiveness. Even though the fact that several research studies imply that competition enhances supply chains, others come to the opposite conclusion, according to the study. This research provides an agent-based modeling technique to understand how rivalry and collaboration between enterprises affect supply chains in the market in which they operate to address this issue. Customers, producers, and suppliers collaborate and compete in a supply chain strategic area, as depicted in the model. The preliminary data described in this research are presented for illustration purposes only. These results reveal that the emergent outcomes are driven by each agent's bounded rationality and that the market structure is predominantly governed by competitive behavior rather than demand.

According to [13], Nigeria's Financial Services (FS) sector has entered a new chapter with the emergence of FinTech (financial services technology). One of the main goals of this research is to shed light on how FinTech technologies are emerging in new areas including next-generation payments, peer-to-peer lending, blockchain, robo-advisory, and financial inclusion in Nigeria. The report also provides a glimpse into Nigeria's FinTech progress and the country's financial and technological centers' adoption of the "fourth industrial revolution." The methodology of the study utilized a technique that draws inspiration from the best-in-class FinTech ecosystems of the developed economies of Singapore, Singapore, Israel, Australia, and Hong Kong. The outcome demonstrates that there is a future for fintech businesses in Nigeria and that the growth is exponential yet

devoid of obvious obstacles like investors, tangible profit models, etc. The report does not, however, offer a methodology that would help Nigeria's fintech companies grow.

[4] Looked at a management challenge involving competition. He believes that managers are torn between placing their people to compete against one another or to collaborate with or within the organization. Individuals and teams can be motivated to be the best via internal competition, resulting in constant incremental performance improvements. Internal collaboration, on the other hand, can lead to effective problem solving through knowledge sharing and innovation.

This study examined the primary determinants of internal competition and internal collaboration adoption, the effects of implementing each strategy, the differences in internal competition and internal collaboration levels at various management levels, and the viability of a hybrid strategy that combines both management philosophies. A qualitative exploratory study involved in-depth interviews with twenty top CEOs. These research results prompted the creation of a hybrid model, which shows that while the two management styles provide different results, there is an ideal approach to combine them to give managers the ability to maximize the performance of both their workers and the company.

[14] Carried out research on the collaborative economy. The collaborative economy allows people to connect online and exchange goods and services. This contribution to policy I provide a definition of the collaborative economy, (ii) a summary of the research on its potential advantages for European economies, (iii) an analysis of the effects of specific platforms in the industries in which they operate, (iii) an explanation of the criteria that can be used to distinguish between professional and non-professional services provided through collaborative platforms, and (iv) suggestions for the platforms so they can create a secure and open collaborative environment. However, the study had little impact on the development of a collaborative business model.

[15] Investigated various potential relationships between banks and Fintech firms. When compared to product/service, investment, merger and acquisition, and other possibilities, collaboration appears to be the most common choice for relationships between banks and Fintech startups, accounting for more than half of the engagements. The study discovered that when traditional banks and Fintech businesses work together, traditional banks are able to use the potential of the products or systems given by Fintech companies. The study cited for example, that Robo-advice Fintech and banks collaborate in the development of innovative investment management services. The study concluded that collaboration would also serve as the cornerstone for joint ventures to develop the digital market and test new technologies and solutions. However, the study failed to demonstrate how collaboration can work effectively.

Based on stakeholder analysis, [2] investigated competition and collaboration in mobile banking. He believes that information and communication technologies (ICT) are always creating new sorts of marketplaces and new patterns of industrial dynamics and that the continued progress of mobile technology allows mobile carriers and banks the possibility to offer mobile banking services. The project investigates how these relationships were formed and developed.

The study's findings show that the mutuality of advantages and costs experienced by stakeholders of the mobile services under examination contributes to the services' success. Furthermore, the formation of a customer base, as well as strong support and interest from stakeholders to facilitate effective collaborations, are critical to the success of mobile banking. As a result, our research helps to clarify how and why mobile carriers and banks collaborate and compete in the area of mobile banking services.

However, because each of them may have different and occasionally conflicting interests, such convergence of services from mobile carriers and banks poses several challenges that are not always easy to address. This article investigates how mobile carrier-bank partnerships were formed and developed in Korea, as well as the perspectives of stakeholders on these agreements. The findings show that the mutuality of advantages and costs experienced by the stakeholders of the mobile services under research, the development of a client base, and strong support and interest from the stakeholders all contribute to the services' success.

[16] looked into how stakeholders should position the fintech sector for success both now and after the crisis and how to maximize Nigeria's Fintech potential. The fact that only 60 million Nigerians have bank accounts, the difficulty in accessing services, particularly in rural areas, the difficulty in finding affordable options, and the poor user experience all add to the irritation that customers face across the board. Fintech companies have seized the opportunity to offer enhanced propositions along the entire value chain to address issues with, among others, quick loans, flexible savings and investments, and reasonable payments. Fintech companies have taken advantage of this opening. Younger people, more smartphone usage, and focused government initiatives to enhance financial inclusion and cashless transactions are all contributing to the favorable conditions that are fostering a thriving fintech sector.

The conclusion of their study suggests that if banks want to be competitive and appealing in a market that is changing, they must embrace technology and transform into nimble, customer-centric companies. Angel investors, venture capital firms, and private equity firms are some of the financing sources that can help Nigerian fintech realize its full potential. Sadly, despite the recent surge in activity within Nigeria's fintech sector and its positive multiplier effect on the economy, there remains enormous potential for growth. Fintech accounted for just 1.25 percent of retail banking revenues in 2019 [17]. Furthermore, the \$460 million in fintech investments made in Nigeria in 2019

represented a relatively small fraction of the \$36 billion in fintech investments made globally, even if the majority of these investments came from foreign sources [18].

The [19] examined the condition of fintech in Nigeria. The paper examines significant developments in the Nigerian fintech market and evaluates the industry's growth drivers and roadblocks. In-depth interviews with industry experts and executives from regulatory agencies and fintech companies were performed as part of the study, which also incorporates comprehensive desk research and interview insights. In-person meetings were place in January and February of 2020. The outcome demonstrates that by 2022, Fintech revenues are anticipated to reach an estimated US\$543m, driven by rising smartphone penetration and the population's unbanked rate. The fact that Nigerian fintechs are expanding beyond payments into loans, microinvestment, wealth management, peer-to-peer transfers, and insurance is another important development. However, some of the difficulties faced by Nigerian fintechs are shared with those in other areas of the world. Companies whose priorities are product excellence and rapidly growing market share frequently lack clarity regarding the road to profitability. While neo-banks in other markets, such as Revolute in the UK and N26 in Germany, have not yet articulated a clear business model, mainstream banks may be able to adopt their digital advances in the future [20].

According to [21], even though a strategic alliance can boost both organizations against outsiders while weakening one partner vis-à-vis the other, the case for collaboration is greater than ever. Taking into account all of the flaws and having examined these various positions and viewpoints, this research will investigate collaboration and competition strategies and develop a hybridized model to demonstrate how much collaboration and intense competition strategy is required for business growth and sustainability using the Nigerian banking sector as a case study.

[22] Propose a tool for evaluating the environment of the fintech industry. The scholarly literature on the environment assessment of the FinTech sector was systematically analyzed, and quantitative methodologies were applied for the study's empirical investigation. The Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) method was used in conjunction with the PEST analysis, expert assessment, determination of indicators' values, normalization of data, and multi-criteria assessment. The study's findings demonstrate that the developed assessment tool's practical application is confirmed by carrying out an empirical study using the examples of both the Baltic States and the top FinTech nations.

The findings demonstrate that policymakers in various nations can utilize the proposed evaluation technique for the FinTech sector's growth to pinpoint the external environmental elements that need to be improved in order to foster the sector's growth. The study makes recommendations for further growth of the Lithuanian FinTech industry. The research has several limitations because it is based on an assessment of the importance of external environmental

indicators of FinTech sector development on a national basis. Only a small portion of the components and nations were chosen for the research due to the high number of indicators and countries. As a result, further research on the research subject is necessary.

[3] Investigate the formation and development of alliances between mobile carriers and banks in Korea and analyze these alliances from the standpoint of stakeholders. The study was inspired by the competition and collaboration that has resulted from the continuous advancement of mobile technologies between mobile carriers and banks for mobile banking services, as well as how information and communication technologies (ICT) have continuously created new types of markets and industry dynamics. However, because each of them may have different and occasionally conflicting interests, such convergence of services from mobile carriers and banks poses several challenges that are not always easy to address. The study's findings revealed that the mutuality of advantages and costs experienced by the stakeholders of the mobile services under examination, the development of a customer base, and strong support and interest from the stakeholders all contribute to the services' success.

The Emerging Role of Data and FinTech in the Development of the Digital Economy and the Regulatory Implications was the subject of research conducted by NCC (2021). According to the survey, there are currently between 210 and 250 FinTech operators and firms working in Nigeria. As a result of these participants, the industry was valued at \$153.1 million in 2017 and is expected to reach \$543.3 million by 2022. Fin-tech start-ups in Nigeria still face a number of challenges to their adoption, use, and acceptability in Nigeria despite these impressive statistics, including bridging the gap between Fin-Tech companies and traditional banking systems, the regulatory environment, collaboration, partnerships & funding, access to financial infrastructure, winning customer trust, and access to talent. The study does not, however, offer a strategy for resolving the problems that were found.

[23] Closely examines the narratives and the level of competition in Nigeria between Fintechs and the banking industry. The study evaluates the current and anticipated trends in Nigeria's banking industry with a focus on fintech and digital banking, as well as the impact of the changing global competitive landscape on the country's banking sector. The study offers guidance for traditional banks and fintech participants on handling new trends. While analyzing the status and growth of the fintech firms, and the strength the collaboration between the traditional banks could bring, the study fails to propose a model or develop a model for such collaboration.

III. DATA AND METHODS

A. *This Section Discusses the Operational Framework that Exists.*

➤ *Collaboration- the New Competition*

Traditional banks and fintech companies both serve as financial intermediaries. Even though banks have been around for hundreds of years, they nevertheless need to adapt to satisfy the needs of modern customers. Fintechs provide users with more features and practically all of the same services that traditional banks do. Fintech is unlikely to completely replace banks in people's lives. Conversely, if fintech and banks could work together and communicate, they could have a bigger impact.

One tactic used by traditional banks is collaboration in the expansion of Fintech companies. Collaboration and co-innovation are critical elements in the relationship between the financial services and technology industries, enabling companies to find ways to grow in the market with their alliances by selecting diverse players. In addition, financial services providers have long found that collaborating with businesses in the same sector is a terrific strategy to expand their market reach while simultaneously reducing expenses. For example, in 1966 a consortium of banks created MasterCard, the most widely used interbank card payment service available to consumers. Superior payment customer service was developed as a result of this relationship [24].

Collaboration benefits Fintech startups as well as traditional banks, according to [25]. Fintech technology assist change consumer mindset and behavior by enabling clients to access far more convenient services online. The utilization of Fintech firms' advanced technologies and flexibility can potentially enhance the client experience for traditional banks. Working together also creates a strong base for progress and creativity. Fintech companies can also reach a large customer base by selling their products in order to grow and expand over time. Fintech may also learn how to negotiate a challenging regulatory landscape by cooperating [25].

Both parties will immediately profit if they can cooperate. Fintech's innovation and agility benefit traditional banks, while their corporate size, long-standing network, and decades of client devotion contribute to increased trust in financial technology. There are various benefits to fintech and traditional institutions working together:

- Compared to fintech, banks have larger deposits. Banks will find it easier to build better financial systems if they work together;
- Fintech and banks will be regulated by the same government bodies, which will foster trust; and
- The traditional financial system will benefit from the superior technology that fintech can bring to banking.

In order to meet today's technological demands, banks are implementing fintech technologies to enhance the client experience. As the entire financial system continues to

evolve, banks are placing an increasing amount of emphasis on digital agility. Long-term collaborations that bring together fintech innovation with banks' backing and confidence to build the digital future's sector result in a win-win scenario.

➤ *Types of Collaboration*

The Information Age has completely changed how business is done [26]. Fortunately, the method of collaboration for innovation has also been subject to advancements in technology. Organizations begin by taking into account a number of elements as they consider their make-or-buy decisions. Time, resources, and talent are all important. Alliances, portfolios, innovation networks, and ecosystem collaborations are the four main types of business cooperation. The four primary types of corporate collaboration are briefly described, along with the significance of each, as follows:

• *Alliances*

The most basic and established form of collaboration connected to innovation is the strategic alliance. Strategic alliances are agreements between two or more independent companies that temporarily combine resources and efforts to achieve their strategic goals.

As international corporations in IT began to run against the limits of their own internal resources in the 1970s and 1980s, alliances began to get attention. They started using these resources to boost their competitiveness and accomplish ever-more difficult objectives.

✓ *The following were the Major Justifications for Forming a Strategic Partnership to Ensure Ongoing Innovation:*

- Make up for technological or organizational limitations;
- Create new product lines and portfolios;
- Successfully enter new markets;
- Provide better customer service; and cut down on NPD (New Product Development) expenses, risks, and time.

Collaboration in the strategic alliance means establishing formal, comprehensive legal agreements that enable businesses to exert significant influence on their partners. Various tactics were employed, including technology sharing, team projects, and stock stakes, to gain greater influence over a partner's innovation initiatives. Naturally, to turn a profit as well. Even with the predominance of formal control, the advantages of cooperation and looser coordination began to surface. To put it another way, collaboration increased.

• *Portfolios*

The portfolio is the second kind of collaborative organization, which is still often employed today. Firms were now interested in extending the benefits of alliances after realizing their advantages. As a result, alliances started to be centrally managed, and portfolio building became more popular.

As a matter of fact, portfolio management was all about internalizing top strategies learned from alliance experiences. A so-called ego firm (also known as a focused firm) entered into agreements with independent companies during this process, but afterward managed the knowledge flows through particular functions.

Large pharmaceutical businesses have historically been great portfolio builders. In order to assimilate information and patents in the most effective and efficient way possible at the beginning of the industry, major companies frequently worked in partnership with tiny biotechnology companies. While disagreements were common at first—small biotechs frequently felt "robbed" of their essential resources—collaboration advanced. The secret to this accomplishment was using portfolio management methods that worked. Overall, the popularity of portfolio management led to a change in how people viewed their colleagues. Later, this mindset would evolve into the "co-creation" perspective.

- *Innovation Networks*

The network is the third form of innovation-related collaboration. Networks are made up of organizations that have similar Research and Development (R&D) objectives for goods, services, procedures, or business models.

Alliances and portfolios naturally progress into dense network architectures. New methods of organizing the invention activity arose as collaboration tools and practices moved from high-tech to medium- and low-tech sectors. The main change was that all businesses were now networked, orchestration was less rigid, and violent survival fights were replaced with low-to-medium levels of competitiveness.

Over time, networks began to compete with one another, whereas suppliers, collaborators, rivals, and even customers might now make novel and unexpected contributions to the creative process. Additionally, businesses were no longer concerned with overseeing personal alliances and connections. They were now taking care of their network posture.

Although coordination costs were higher, networks' usefulness quickly became clear. Networks were primarily employed for

- ✓ Search for technology advancements in the business environment;
- ✓ Enhance individual and group skills; and
- ✓ Ensure long-term survival.
- ✓ Overall, networks emphasized the collaborators' overall well-being much more.

- *Ecosystems*

The ecosystem is the fourth and most sophisticated kind of collaboration for invention. Companies like Salesforce, a provider of client relationship management software, IMEC, a manufacturer of nanoelectronics, Korean Air, and ENEL, a distributor of electricity and gas, are just a few examples of how ecosystems can and should be used to create value that no one company alone can produce.

[26] Notes that while there is no widely agreed-upon definition of ecosystems, the highlighted key characteristics of ecosystems include their long-term orientation, ability to partially self-adjust, and ability to make complex interdependencies between various types of partners, including end customers, explicit.

A loosely connected network of businesses and other organizations that grow their capabilities around a common set of technologies, information, or skills and collaborate and compete to create new goods and services is an ecosystem collaborative business model [26]. It is a system that is mostly self-contained, self-adjusting, and connected through shared institutional structures and mutual value generation through service exchange amongst resource-integrating actors. For two reasons, the ecosystem collaborative business model is regarded as being of utmost significance: the interactions between members of an ecosystem are defined by a set of rules and standards, and the value of an ecosystem is solely established by the collaborator(s) or client (s). Innovation is therefore no longer beneficial to the focus firm. Today, innovation is a collaborative process.

In general, ecosystems are often distinguished by: a lack of formal authority, strong member dependency, a shared set of (complementary) aims and objectives, and a shared set of knowledge and skills.

In a shared enterprise, serving one another, assisting one another in creating value, committing to one another, and pursuing jointly developed objectives and goals are the norm in an ecosystem collaborative business model.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

A. *Competitive Forces Model*

In strategic analysis, the Competitive Forces Model is a valuable tool for examining industry competitiveness. Porter's Five Forces Model is more commonly known for covering the following five forces: intensity of rivalry, the threat of possible new entrants, buyer negotiating strength, supplier bargaining power, and the threat of alternative goods and or services.

By evaluating an industry's structure, the Five Forces study is often used to examine firm strategy, vulnerabilities, and strengths. The five forces are commonly used to evaluate the competitive intensity, attractiveness, and profitability of an industry or market. A company's profitability is influenced by the size and power of its competitors, possible new market entrants, suppliers, customers, and replacement products. However, as much as businesses use Porter's five-force model to do an environmental analysis, these businesses must be balanced both internally and externally, which is a condition that is commonly lacking. The five-force paradigm is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig 1 Five Forces Model
(Source: [27])

According to [4], many organizations have been unjustly drawn into undue alliances when their fundamental need remains to sharpen their competitive drive, rather than dull it through collaboration with other firms. However, a new school of strategic thinking has evolved, emphasizing the positive importance of collaborative rather than competitive agreements amongst industry actors [11]. Organizations leaders are realizing that even their best individual efforts are insufficient to address today's complex and interwoven issues, and are beginning to put their interests aside and work together to create a new business infrastructure that will help them achieve their common goals [2]. The reality is that both Competition and Collaboration have weaknesses, and hybridizing both can help build organisation strength in today's complex market.

V. CONCLUSION

Competitive-Collaboration seems to be the best course of action in the competition between two complementary organizations as opposed to going head-to-head. Organizations leaders are realizing that even their best individual efforts are insufficient to address today's complex and interwoven issues and are beginning to put their interests aside and work together to create a new business infrastructure that will help them achieve their common goals. Conversely, many organizations have also been unjustly drawn into these alliances when their fundamental need remains to sharpen their competitive drive, rather than dull it through collaboration with other firms. The reality is that both Competition and Collaboration have weaknesses and a good mix of these business models will be of advantage to any organization.

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